

A schema to calculate MIDS scores

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(MI) MIDS - A digitisation standard for natural history collections, Lecture Theatre 1, Appleton Tower, 11 Crichton Street, EH8 9LE, June 7, 2022, 9:30 AM - 11:00 AM

The MIDS standard (Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen) is an emerging TDWG standard currently in development to quantify the digitization status of natural history specimens. Depending on the available data on these specimens, a MIDS level of 0 ('bare') up to 3 ('extended') may be assigned. MIDS levels should be calculable in different contexts, from local databases for digitized collection data to large aggregating repositories such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF).

We propose a schema that maps between the source data model and the MIDS properties, taking into account known values for missing, withheld or undeciphered data elements and allowing for MIDS calculations to be made in a documented and reproducible manner. The schema is flexible and can be adjusted for different data standards and different interpretations of these standards, as is for instance not uncommon with implementations of Darwin Core. Also, the schema can be modified as the MIDS standard matures further in its development, allowing it to serve as a testing tool for the implications of adjusted, added or removed properties.

To illustrate the operation of this schema, we developed a tool that makes use of it to calculate MIDS scores for a given dataset and provides visualisations and analyses of these scores. The workflow behind this tool could eventually be integrated into existing data publishing tools such as the IPT or Biocase, introducing MIDS into specimen data pipelines that are already in operation.

References

Hardisty, A., Addink, W., Dillen, M., Groom, Q., Haston, E., et al. (Draft) Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen (MIDS) v0.14, 29 Mar 2021. <https://github.com/tdwg/mids>

